

THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING COURSE

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Annotation: The article describes the methodology of higher school students' professional competences development with application of interactive teaching methods, including system, activity, facilitation, competence-based approaches and the theory of contextual learning. Based on these approaches and existing principles of teaching adapted to the educational process, the author considers some groups of methods supporting formation of components of the professional competence of students.

Keywords: professional competence, structure of professional competence, student, interactive communication, interactive methods, development of professional competence.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрена методология процесса формирования профессиональных компетенций студентов высшей школы в условиях использования интерактивных методов обучения, заключающаяся в применении системного, деятельностного, фасилитационного, компетентностного подходов и теории контекстного обучения. На основе данных подходов и адаптированных к образовательному процессу существующих принципов обучения выделены группы методов, способствующие формированию отдельных составляющих профессиональной компетенции студентов.

Ключевые слова: профессиональные компетенции, структура профессиональной компетенции, студент, интерактивное взаимодействие, интерактивные методы, формирование профессиональной компетенции.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada o'qitishning interfaol usullarini qo'llash orqali ta'lim oluvchilarining kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish metodologiyasi, jumladan tizim, faoliyat, yordam berish, kompetensiyaga asoslangan yondashuvlar va kontekstli ta'lim nazariyasi tasvirlangan. Ushbu yondashuvlar va ta'lim jarayoniga moslashtirilgan o'qitishning mavjud tamoyillariga asoslanib, muallif o'quvchilarning kasbiy kompetensiyasi tarkibiy qismlarini shakllantirishni qo'llab-quvvatlovchi usullarning ayrim guruhlarini ko'rib chiqadi.

Kalit so'zlar: kasbiy kompetensiya, kasbiy kompetensiya tarkibi, talaba, interfaol muloqot, interfaol usullar, kasbiy kompetensiyani rivojlantirish.

Introduction

The article presents theoretical and empirical results of studying the professional competence of students in terms of interactive learning. The study shows that the conducted research is extremely important for the successful and on-time implementation of the main goals in relation to the reformed system of education and vocational training. The author considers the interactive presentation of educational material, which is increasingly used in the system of higher education. The article describes the types of interactive learning and shows their impact on the formation of training and professionally important qualities of

students. Professional competence is considered as a multifaceted phenomenon, its development by means of interactive learning is the main criterion for the successful organization of the current educational process at the university and the professional formation of personality.

The competency-based approach is by definition aimed at the result of education, the result is considered to be the nature of the acquired information and the ability of a person to use the acquired knowledge in various situations, which will manifest itself in the future as professional competence. "Professional competence is understood as an integral characteristic that determines the ability of a specialist to solve professional problems and typical professional tasks that arise in real situations of professional activity, using knowledge, professional and life experience, values and inclinations" [4].

For the effective formation of professional competencies in a graduate, it is necessary to use teaching technologies that require independence of students, dialogicity and changes in the nature of interaction of all subjects of the educational process, activation of the students' activities during the lesson, bringing the topics studied closer to real life and searching for ways to solve emerging problems.

Note that competencies are formed only in the experience of one's own activity, therefore it is necessary to form and develop such qualities in students as independence, responsibility, cognitive, creative, communicative and personal activity. Therefore, in the educational process of the university it is necessary to actively introduce active and interactive methods and forms of teaching and conducting classes in combination with extracurricular work.

Methods

Interactive forms of work provide an opportunity to introduce real professional activity situations into the learning process, with the help of which students solve various types of problems and analyze situations, which confirms one of the requirements for the conditions of implementation of the main educational programs of the bachelor's degree based on the Federal State Educational Standard: "wide use in the educational process of active and interactive forms of conducting classes in combination with extracurricular work."

Interactive learning preserves the final goal and the main content of the educational process but modifies the forms from transmitting (transfer) to dialogical, that is, based on mutual understanding and interaction.

The solution to the problem of creating a positive interaction of educational subjects is associated with the definition of options for using specific interactive methods and forms of training (S.A. Bizyaeva, A.M. Bolgova, T.N. Dobrynina, O.A. Kim, N.E. Sedova, etc.). The organization of interactive learning is considered in the studies of L.K. Geykhman, I.M. Gorbachenko, I.A. Goryainova, I.A. Dmitrieva, M.V. Klarin, E.V. Korotaeva, A.V. Kosharny, V.V. Chistov and others, in which this type of training appears as a means and a condition for the development of cognitive activity of students, and as a factor in the pedagogical interaction of subjects of the educational process.

Discussion and results

As a result of using interactive methods, the following tasks of the educational process are solved, in particular:

1) strengthening motivation, activating interest in studying the disciplines provided for by the plan;

- 2) increasing the efficiency and optimality of assimilation of educational material;
- 3) approximation and compliance of the presented educational information with the sphere of future practical activity;
- 4) teaching independence in searching for ways and options for solving the task (problem) set before them;
- 5) teaching respect for the rights of the participant in the interaction to their own opinion;
- 6) formation of life and professional skills.

Interactive methods are characterized by extensive interaction of students, both with the teacher and with each other. The predominant, dominant in this nature of education is the activity of students in the learning process. The role of the teacher is characterized by directing the students' activities to achieve the goals of the lesson, to activate the educational and cognitive activity of students, intensive development of cognitive motives, creative abilities.

Therefore, with interactive methods, it is not so much the acquisition of knowledge that is important, but the formation of skills, abilities, personal qualities, and the ability to apply them in social and professional activities, that is, the formation of a certain system of student competencies. Of particular importance in this case is the formation of analytical, research, and communication skills, the development of the ability to analyze a situation, plan a strategy, and make optimal decisions (presented in the content of the Federal State Educational Standard for the area of training). Therefore, the use of the method involves modeling real-life, social, and professional situations, joint analysis, and solving the proposed problems.

Currently, scientists distinguish three types of interactive learning used in the educational process.

The first type of interactive learning involves the interaction of the student and the subject of study. It is assumed that the student increases the level of his or her intellectual development by "communicating with himself or herself" about ideas, information obtained from a textbook, lecture, or TV show. To do this, students must have the following learning tools: educational audio and video materials, computer programs, texts.

In the second type of interactive learning, the student interacts with the teacher. The teacher, following the program of the taught discipline, helps to increase the student's interest in the material being studied, causing him to be motivated to study.

The student studies certain informative material that demonstrates how to apply the acquired knowledge, modeling certain approaches. Then the teacher creates a situation in which the student can show how he independently applies the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities. During the interaction, the student, relying on the help of the teacher, can determine the strategy for studying the discipline.

In the third version of the application of the interactive method, students interact in various situations. Students learn the skills of group work, use the principles of group interaction during the relevant trainings.

The essence of interactive teaching methods, as noted by L.A. Peskova, is to organize the educational process in such a way that almost all students are involved in the process of cognition, having the opportunity to reflect on their knowledge and skills [1, 3, 5].

Thus, the essence of the organization of interactive learning is that it provides an opportunity for all subjects of the educational process to be involved in the process of communication as a polylogue, to express their value opinions, to exchange information and skill models, which allows them to become full participants in the educational process from the inside. The role of the teacher is to determine the high-quality appropriate conditions for maintaining optimal activity of students, to become an assistant in organizing work in class and to be a high-quality source of information, the initiator of discussions and debates. It can be concluded that interactive learning contributes to more effective assimilation of educational information by students, the development of communicative competence and personality traits necessary for a bachelor of psychological and pedagogical training. This is ensured by the fact that:

- interactive learning methods model the content of psychological, pedagogical and social and pedagogical activity
- acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities occurs in the process of equal dialogic communication in an atmosphere of trust and understanding;
- participants in the educational process provide each other with various types of support;
- the content of the educational material optimally stimulates joint search and creative solution of educational problems [1, 3, 5].

The main types and methods of interactive teaching methods include: brainstorming, lectures, role-playing and business games, discussions, modeling (simulation games), debates, round tables, case studies, master classes, project method, trainings, etc. [7, 8].

Interactive educational technologies can be based on the problem-based teaching method, which activates the educational and research work of the future bachelor and allows to obtain in-depth knowledge and skills necessary for the successful professional activity of graduates.

It is important to direct the educational process to the analysis of specific situations, the resolution of identified contradictions and problems by searching for and substantiating options for their solution based on using knowledge of social, political and professional phenomena and processes. The method of analyzing specific professional situations is called the case method (case study). Case technology develops the cognitive interests, creative abilities of students, including them in an active dialogue, processing and analysis of information characterizing various problem situations. Case technology provides a choice, develops the activity of students, forms cognitive interest, the ability to assess their capabilities, develops independence, creativity, initiative. Classes using the "case study" technology can become a necessary addition to the study of new material, individual assignment completion and group work [6].

A case (situational exercise) contains a problem that should be comprehensively studied, analyzed, and a specific solution should be proposed, justified by a number of conditions and criteria. Analysis of a case situation, solution of a theoretical or practical problem contained in this case involves searching for and justifying various possible options for answers to the questions of this problem.

Development and analysis of cases, scenarios of business, role-playing games, classes conducted using the small group method can be organized in different ways and used for

various purposes. Developed cases and other materials can also be used as homework with a discussion of its results in class or analysis of a written assignment.

As part of the case technology, a whole range of active teaching methods is implemented, including: the project method (in game design, students are organized into small groups to discuss innovative ideas; in a master class, students analyze various case situations; in training, situations are played out in roles) [6].

Training is a form and method of interactive learning, the purpose of which is to develop competence in interpersonal and professional behavior in communication: it is during training that all participants in the educational process can be actively involved in the learning process.

In the practice of preparing bachelors in the aspect of the competence approach, it is possible to use skill-based, socio-psychological and other types of training.

Accordingly, skill-based training ensures the formation and development of certain skills and abilities. In our aspect, these are the skills of interaction, building contact, etc.

Socio-psychological training (SPT) occupies an intermediate position, it is aimed at changes in both consciousness and in the formation of skills. SPT mainly ensures a change in social attitudes and the development of skills and experience in the field of interpersonal communication.

The main goal of social and psychological training - improving communication competence - can be specified in a number of tasks with different formulations, but necessarily related to the acquisition of knowledge, the formation of skills, abilities, the development of attitudes that determine behavior in communication, human perceptual abilities, correction and development of the system of personal relationships, since personal originality is the background that colors a person's actions in different colors, all his verbal and non-verbal manifestations. The use of interactive teaching technologies in the classroom ensures not only the successful assimilation of educational material by all students, intellectual, but also the creative development of students, their independence, activity. Interactive learning is a special form of organizing cognitive activity. It has in mind very specific and predictable goals. One of these goals is to create comfortable learning conditions in which the student feels his success, his intellectual solvency, which makes the learning process itself productive and gives each student the opportunity to reveal himself, develop his creative abilities and self-actualize as a person [2].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the use of these methods in the educational process allows making the student an active participant, forming and developing the cognitive activity of students, their self-reflection. The use of active and interactive methods contributes to the formation of a creative, active personality, capable of adapting to the modern, constantly changing world. The advantage of interactive teaching methods is that they awaken the interest of students, contribute to the effective assimilation of material, have a multifaceted impact, form life skills, high motivation and strength of knowledge, develop imagination, creativity, communication skills. Students develop team spirit, individuality, the ability to express themselves. These methods teach activity and mutual respect. As the practice of the educational process shows, interactive teaching methods allow you to relieve the nervous strain of students, provide a unique opportunity to change the forms of activity and focus on the main tasks and issues of the lesson.

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